

1 Methods and strategies for tackling 2 assay interference associated with 3 small molecules

4 Lu Tan¹, Steffen Hirte^{2,3}, Vincenzo Palmacci^{2,3}, Conrad Stork^{4#} and Johannes Kirchmair^{2,5*}

5 ¹ Drug Discovery Sciences, Boehringer Ingelheim RCV GmbH & Co KG, 1121 Vienna,
6 Austria

7 ² Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Division of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Faculty of
8 Life Sciences, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

9 ³ Vienna Doctoral School of Pharmaceutical, Nutritional and Sport Sciences (PhaNuSpo),
10 University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

11 ⁴ Department of Informatics, Center for Bioinformatics, Faculty of Mathematics, Informatics
12 and Natural Sciences, Universität Hamburg, 20146 Hamburg, Germany

13 ⁵ Christian Doppler Laboratory for Molecular Informatics in the Biosciences, Department for
14 Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

15 # Current affiliation: BASF SE, Ludwigshafen am Rhein 67063, Germany

16

17 * Correspondence: email johannes.kirchmair@univie.ac.at, phone +43-1-4277-55104

18 Abstract

19 Biochemical and cell-based assays are essential to discovering and optimising efficacious
20 and safe drugs, agrochemicals and cosmetics. However, false assay readouts stemming from
21 colloidal aggregation, chemical reactivity, chelation, light signal attenuation and emission,
22 membrane disruption and other interference mechanisms remain significant challenges in
23 screening synthetic compounds and natural products. To address assay interference, a range
24 of powerful experimental approaches and strategies are available. Moreover, *in silico* methods
25 for identifying suspicious assay readouts and predicting likely interference compounds,

26 including rule-based, similarity-based, statistical and machine-learning approaches, are now
27 gaining traction and recognition. This Review begins with a balanced and timely overview of
28 the scope and limitations of experimental and theoretical approaches for tackling assay
29 interference. It then focuses on computational methods, discusses strategies to integrate them
30 with experimental approaches, and provides recommendations for best practices. The Review
31 closes with a summary of the critical facts and learnings and an outlook on possible future
32 developments.

33 Introduction

34 Today, a plethora of biochemical and cell-based assays that allow the experimental testing
35 of small organic compounds for their biological activity are at our disposal. These assay
36 technologies are indispensable to a host of industries, including the pharmaceutical,
37 agrochemical and cosmetics sectors. They are also essential, e.g., to investigating the
38 biological activities of food compounds to understand their beneficial or harmful effects on
39 human health¹.

40 Depending on the specific assay and automation technologies employed, with a certain
41 lead time, up to a million compounds (and even more) can be tested per day. The outcome of
42 such large-scale screening campaigns is unlikely to be a shortage of hits. Quite on the
43 contrary, screening campaigns regularly produce a sizable number of initial hits, of which,
44 however, only a fraction may reflect genuine, specific interactions of the hit compound with a
45 biomacromolecule. In fact, typical screening libraries contain a significant number of 'bad
46 actors', commonly also referred to as 'nuisance compounds', Pan-Assay Interference
47 Compounds (PAINS²), Compounds Interfering with an Assay Technology (CIATs³), or, in the
48 context of natural products research, Invalid Metabolic Panaceas (IMPs⁴). All these terms
49 describe compounds that can cause interference in biological assays, resulting in false-
50 positive or false-negative assay readouts. They are often used interchangeably, although not
51 all are equivalent. Another commonly but often inaccurately used term is 'frequent hitter'⁵,
52 which describes compounds showing higher-than-expected hit rates in distinct biological
53 assays. Frequent hitter behaviour is often, but not always, linked to assay interference (see
54 Box 1 for an overview of relevant terms and definitions).

55 Two major categories of assay interference can be distinguished: generalised interference
56 and technology-related interference. Generalised interference primarily refers to phenomena
57 linked to a compound's physicochemical properties, such as the ability to form colloidal
58 aggregates or undergo chemical reactions. Technology-related assay interference primarily

59 results from the interference of compounds with certain assay signals or components (see Box
60 2 and Refs. ^{2,6-8}). This categorisation can be context-dependent, as assay interference stems
61 from the intricate interplay between a compound and a specific assay component⁹. For
62 example, compounds interfering with fluorescence-based assays because of their
63 autofluorescence may show benign behaviour in assays measuring other types of signals.
64 Therefore, assays based on orthogonal technologies can be particularly useful in hit
65 verification (see section 'Experimental approaches for tackling assay interference').

66 While a lot of the recent discussions of assay interference are focused on biochemical
67 assays, it should be noted that assay artefacts are also of considerable concern to cell-based
68 assays¹⁰⁻¹³. In particular, cytotoxicity can lead to false-positive or false-negative results.^{10,12,14}
69 Therefore, factors influencing cellular fitness¹², such as general cytotoxicity, genotoxicity,
70 membrane integrity and mitochondrial toxicity, may need to be checked as a source of
71 interference in cell-based assays.

72 A critical, still often underappreciated source of assay interference is compound breakdown
73 products and impurities^{15,16}. They are particularly challenging to predict, trace, handle and
74 exclude (see Box 2).

75 Without proper study design and controls, the fraction of hits obtained during the initial
76 compound screening that are artefacts can be as high as 80% or even approach 100%^{17,18}. If
77 these false hits remain undetected, they can trigger expensive hit expansion and hit-to-lead
78 follow-up studies^{2,18,19}. Such efforts will likely be futile because the observed poor or even
79 misleading structure-activity relationship will impede the rational optimisation of the biological
80 properties of a compound. Especially problematic is scientific literature in which compounds
81 are falsely reported as active. Such errors have a good chance of propagation, particularly if
82 the compounds wrongly assumed to be bioactive are readily obtainable from commercial or
83 noncommercial sources for further studies^{20,21}. The scientific community and the publishers
84 have recognised this problem. In 2017, the editors-in-chief of nine American Chemical Society
85 (ACS) journals focusing on topics related to small-molecule drug discovery published an
86 editorial with guidelines and recommendations on how to detect bad actors and avoid their
87 emergence as wrongly assumed bioactive compounds in the literature¹⁷. The editorial
88 represents an important step in raising awareness about the problem of assay interference.
89 However, with today's advanced understanding of the complexities of assay interference, and
90 in line with concerns voiced following its publication²², some of the statements encouraging
91 the use of theoretical approaches, specifically the PAINS concept (discussed below), would
92 require updates and refinements. This is even more true for some of the author guidelines

93 defined by leading journals in the field, which tend to overrate the reliability and scope of the
94 PAINS concept as a means to minimise false reports of bioactive compounds.

95 Assay interference may impede the rational optimisation of compounds, but most types of
96 assay interference are not necessarily detrimental to the value of a drug. In fact, assay
97 interference phenomena have been described for a significant number of marketed drugs. For
98 example, O'Donnell et al.²³ found 19 out of 56 investigated drugs to form colloidal aggregates
99 and further 14 to show problematic behaviour. Given that the conditions to which drugs are
100 exposed *in vivo* (e.g. compound concentrations and composition of solutions) differ
101 fundamentally from those present in biochemical assays²⁴, the observed interferences'
102 relevance is likely low. However, negative implications on pharmacokinetics cannot be
103 categorically excluded²⁵.

104 Assay interference is not a problem exclusive to synthetic compounds. On the contrary,
105 many chemotypes found in natural products have been linked to assay interference²⁶. For
106 example, one of the most widely occurring flavonoids in nature, quercetin, is known to disrupt
107 biomembranes^{27,28}, interfere with spectroscopic assays^{2,29}, and form colloidal aggregates³⁰. It
108 has been reported as active in over half of several hundred assays deposited in PubChem
109 BioAssay⁴, many of which represent pharmaceutically relevant proteins. Doxorubicin, an
110 anthraquinone produced by *Streptomyces* strains, is known to be redox-active, undergo
111 reactions with nucleophiles, and interfere with fluorescence-based assays²⁶. The natural
112 product has been reported as active in 85% of 4000 bioassays³¹. Whereas quercetin is used
113 occasionally as a food supplement, doxorubicin has a decades-long record of use as a
114 chemotherapeutic for treating various cancers³². Fortunately, the development of doxorubicin
115 was not thwarted by its assay interference behaviour. These examples illustrate just how
116 complex the correct interpretation of assay interference behaviour can be.

117 While in medicinal chemistry, the primary concern is about false-positive assay readouts, it
118 should be noted that although less common, false-negative results can also be problematic.
119 They can lead to the missing of valuable starting points for drug discovery, and, more
120 importantly, in toxicological screening, they may occlude potentially harmful effects.

121 Today, a range of powerful experimental approaches for tackling assay interference has
122 been established, and *in silico* methods are gaining traction and recognition. The integration
123 of these two domains holds the potential for significant synergistic effects. It will play a pivotal
124 role in effectively overcoming the challenges posed by assay interference.

125 This Review aims to provide an insightful overview of the scope and limitations of these
126 methods. It begins with a concise introduction of assay interference, followed by an outline of

127 the most relevant and established experimental approaches before proceeding, in detail, with
128 computational techniques and tools. Later parts of the Review discuss strategies for
129 integrating experimental and theoretical approaches and provide recommendations for best
130 practices. The final part summarises the most critical facts and considerations, and provides
131 an outlook on possible future developments.

132 Experimental approaches for tackling assay 133 interference

134 Experts in biological assay technologies know the risks of interference from small organic
135 compounds. Therefore, they usually build screening campaigns on two or more conceptually
136 and technologically distinct assays, ideally complemented by *in silico* approaches (see the
137 section 'Integrating theoretical and experimental approaches), to support hit triage^{9,12,13,33–36}.
138 Here, we discuss the most relevant screening components and anti-interference strategies.
139 An overview of experimental approaches for tackling assay interference is provided in Box 3.

140 Primary screening assays are utilised to rapidly screen large compound libraries, usually
141 employing a single measurement per compound. While certain measures are commonly
142 implemented to detect assay interference, there is a potential for significant numbers of false-
143 positive hits to appear in primary screening assays. Consequently, the initial hits typically
144 undergo further testing in follow-up screens, often conducted in triplicate and involving dose
145 titrations. This approach helps alleviate some of the false readouts associated with the rapid
146 screening process. In any case, the relevant hits obtained from the primary screening assay
147 should be subjected to further evaluation in more specialised and informative assays.

148 Counter-screen assays are designed to address and rule out false assay readouts caused
149 by a defined or anticipated type of assay interference. They mimic the assay conditions and
150 reagents of the primary screen to a certain extent, often to elicit an (unspecific) activity signal,
151 but without enabling the actual biological process to occur^{7,12,33,34,37–39} (e.g. by missing or
152 swapping the target biomacromolecule). Typical examples of counter-screen approaches
153 include assays measuring the signal modulation of compounds independent of the target (e.g.
154 measuring compound autofluorescence in fluorescence-based assays) and enzymatic tests
155 such as the AmpC β -lactamase assay for detecting aggregators (the enzyme is sensitive to
156 inhibition by colloidal aggregates). The genuine biological activity of any compound active in
157 both the primary screening and counter-screen assay(s) is questionable, whereas its assay

158 interference is confirmative. However, inactivity in a counter-screen is neither evidence of the
159 absence of other types of interference nor evidence of genuine biological activity.

160 Orthogonal assays are designed to measure the same biological effect or target through
161 different components, technologies or pathways, making them resilient to assay interference
162 of the same kind^{7,12,33,34,39}. For example, a cell-based assay could serve as an orthogonal
163 assay for a biochemical, primary screening assay. This setup can offer deeper insights into a
164 compound's biological, functional and toxicological properties. It is also one of the strongest
165 setups to support computer-guided compound optimisation. Compounds showing activity in
166 both the primary screening assay and orthogonal assay(s) most likely exhibit genuine
167 biological activity on the biomacromolecule of interest, although some uncertainty remains.

168 Depending on the specific use case, orthogonal assays and counter-screens may also be
169 employed in tandem to complement the main screening assay(s)^{9,13}. As a general guideline,
170 when a counter-screen is implemented, compounds active in both the primary assay and the
171 counter-screen should be flagged for de-selection or further vetting in an orthogonal assay.
172 When an orthogonal assay is used, compounds active in both assays should be prioritised for
173 progression.

174 The commonly used anti-interference strategies in primary screen, counter-screen, and
175 orthogonal assays include different assay tuning strategies and kinetic approaches (see
176 Box 3). Screening experts also make extensive use of biophysical methods⁴⁰ such as dynamic
177 light scattering (DLS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray crystallography, surface
178 plasmon resonance (SPR), and microscopy, as well as chemical methods^{38,41} (e.g. scavenging
179 agents to bind chemically reactive compounds). None of these tools and strategies is a
180 panacea against assay interference, as they all come with limitations concerning throughput,
181 reliability, applicability, and costs.

182 Theoretical approaches for identifying potentially 183 false assay readouts

184 Today, several theoretical approaches for identifying potential assay interference events
185 are available⁴². Among these, some of the most potent approaches focus on dose-response
186 curve analysis and curve fitting to check for the presence of features characteristic of assay
187 anomalies, such as a steep hill slope and lack of saturation. Other strategies include
188 substructure and scaffold analyses. They can be even more informative if measured bioactivity

189 data for a set of related compounds or data from different biological assays (which can be
190 translated, e.g. into hit rates) is considered^{2,43,44}. Many existing rule sets were derived utilising
191 such approaches.

192 Approaches building on the similar property principle^{45,46} (which states that structurally
193 related molecules likely have similar properties) enable experts to identify, through statistical
194 means and visualisation, implausible assay readouts and potential inconsistencies in the data.
195 Examples of approaches building on this principle include similarity-based and scaffold-based
196 compound clustering⁴² (which places structurally related compounds into proximity),
197 quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) modelling⁴⁷ (a mathematical approach for
198 predicting the biological properties of compounds based on their molecular structure),
199 matched molecular pair analysis⁴⁸ (an analytical approach to determine the impact of a single
200 chemical transformation observed for a pair of molecules on their properties) and its extension,
201 matched molecular series analysis⁴⁹ (which determines the impact of a single chemical
202 transformation at a specific site based on a set of molecules).

203 The structure–activity landscape index (SALI)⁵⁰ puts the similarity of pairs of molecules
204 concerning their molecular structure and biological activity into perspective: molecular pairs
205 with a high SALI indicate activity cliffs⁵¹ (i.e., pairs of structurally closely related compounds
206 with distinct levels of bioactivity). Activity cliffs can either be genuine (e.g. caused by a steric
207 clash of the compound with residues forming the ligand binding site) or artefacts (e.g.
208 stemming from assay interference, assay variability, mistakes during the experiment or data
209 transfer, and the limitations of molecular representations^{52,53}). A closer look at these outliers
210 is indicated to interpret their meaning correctly.

211 In addition to the cheminformatics approaches discussed in this section, models and
212 approaches designed for predicting assay interference can be employed to flag suspicious
213 assay readouts. These methods are discussed in the following sections.

214 In silico technologies for assay interference 215 prediction

216 *In silico* approaches for assay interference prediction can broadly be classified into rule-
217 based approaches (flagging nuisance compounds based on structural patterns), similarity-
218 based approaches (assessing the molecular similarity of compounds of interest to compounds
219 with known behaviour), statistical approaches (leveraging historical measured bioactivity data

220 to assess, primarily, the frequent-hitter behaviour of compounds), and machine-learning
221 approaches (identifying and weighing molecular properties that influence the behaviour of
222 compounds in biological assays).

223 In this section, we summarise the scope and limitations of these technologies, while in the
224 next section, we discuss publicly available models for assay interference prediction. Because
225 today, the bottleneck in developing and validating *in silico* approaches is usually not the
226 technology but the available measured data, we begin our discussions with a focus on data.

227 Data sources for developing models for assay interference 228 prediction

229 In the context of assay interference prediction, corporate databases are particularly
230 precious to model development because they are usually of significant size, more consistent,
231 and of high density (meaning that a substantial part of the compounds has been measured in
232 the same, extensive set of biological assays). Unfortunately, except for rule sets, models built
233 on this valuable data are rarely, if ever, made accessible to the scientific community.

234 However, recent years have seen a strong community effort towards FAIR data⁵⁴, open
235 data and open access. This effort is reflected by the sizable data sets that are in the public
236 domain today, including PubChem BioAssay⁵⁵, with more than 115 million compounds and
237 close to 300 million measured bioactivities, the ChEMBL database^{56,57}, with a total of 2.4
238 million compounds and more than 20 million measured bioactivities, and the European
239 Chemical Biology Database (ECBD)⁵⁸, with a total of more than 100,000 compounds and more
240 than 1.6 million measured bioactivities. In particular, PubChem BioAssay includes substantial
241 amounts of data from different counter-screen assays, which are regularly used to develop
242 models predicting aggregators or compounds interfering with fluorescence-based or
243 luciferase-based assays⁵⁹⁻⁶³.

244 In addition to the large, public bioactivity data sets, several smaller-sized and focused data
245 sets exist, such as a set of 12 645 known aggregators⁶⁴. These can be difficult to find as they
246 may be 'hidden', e.g., in the supporting information of publications. Search utilities such as
247 Google Dataset Search⁶⁵ can help to find such hidden data gems. A further challenge arises
248 from the fact that much of the data is stored in formats requiring substantial processing.

249 Data biases are of significant concern when developing *in silico* models, particularly
250 machine learning models⁶⁶. For example, research articles are generally skewed towards
251 reporting positive results (in this context, bioactive compounds). This bias regularly propagates

252 into data sets derived from these sources, causing issues related to data set imbalance in
253 model training and validation. Another critical issue is analogue bias, which stems from the
254 fact that drug discovery data often contains congeneric series of compounds. Suppose such
255 congeneric series are split over the training and test sets. In that case, the difficulty presented
256 by the test cases and, hence, the real-world performance of the model will likely be
257 overestimated. Today, this issue is often addressed with a scaffold-split strategy, which
258 enforces the absence of a molecular scaffold overlap between the training and test sets⁶⁷. Of
259 note, there are differing definitions of what constitutes a molecular scaffold, and, depending
260 on the definition, e.g. the change of a single atom element can qualify a structure as a distinct
261 molecular scaffold.

262 Additional challenges arise when combining data from multiple assays, e.g., for the purpose
263 of developing models for frequent hitter prediction. The data set's composition will strongly
264 influence the scope and behaviour of these models. Without corrections, a model trained on
265 a set of bioassays with an apparent surplus in fluorescence-based assays will more likely flag
266 compounds interfering with this assay technology as frequent hitters than compounds causing
267 other types of assay interference. Likewise, data sets with a strong representation of kinase
268 assays may lead to models that classify kinase inhibitors as (undesirable) frequent hitters
269 (even though they may have a favourable multi-kinase inhibition profile). Assay data sets with
270 a strong representation of promiscuous biomacromolecules, such as some cytochrome P450
271 isozymes or transporters, may result in models behaving differently from those trained on
272 classical drug targets. Research on this topic is still in its infancy.

273 A further constraint in using assay datasets for model development is that many do not
274 provide sufficient information to assess whether individual assay readouts reflect genuine
275 bioactivities or artefacts. Also, a problematic portion of positive assay readouts is likely related
276 to undetected impurities, which may be sample-specific (see Box 2). Such effects cannot be
277 modelled based purely on molecular structures (which many *in silico* models rely on
278 exclusively). Together, the insufficiencies of the measured data limit the performance and
279 scope of *in silico* models. Consequently, it is not uncommon to see that the investments made
280 in expertise and labour for data curation and analysis, as well as in model validation, exceed
281 those made in the actual model-building process.

282 Rule-based approaches

283 Rule-based approaches are widely employed in drug discovery for filtering or flagging
284 compounds with undesirable properties related to bioavailability, chemical stability and

285 reactivity, toxicity, metabolism, and assay interference. One of the best-known rule sets in
286 drug discovery is Lipinski's Rule of Five⁶⁸ (describing properties relevant to the oral bioactivity
287 of small-molecule drugs). While the Rule of Five defines thresholds for a set of
288 physicochemical properties, many other rule-based approaches utilise molecular substructure
289 patterns developed, sometimes over years or even decades of research, into comprehensive
290 'dictionaries'. The individual patterns are commonly encoded in the SMARTS language⁶⁹.

291 Many research groups in industry and academia have published (parts of) the rule sets
292 they employ for excluding compounds with undesirable properties in their screening deck.
293 These rule sets focus on identifying chemically reactive compounds and/or frequent hitters^{70–}
294 ⁷⁶. One of the most famous collections of substructure patterns is the PAINS rule set, which
295 encodes molecular scaffold substructures linked to different types of assay interference^{2,77}. In
296 toxicology, rules are widely employed and typically referred to as 'structural alerts'^{78–80}. Among
297 the most comprehensive pattern collections overall is the ZINC20 pattern set^{81,82}. It comprises
298 1468 patterns, including the 480 PAINS patterns, 114 patterns for named functional groups,
299 62 linked to benign reagents (building blocks), and 57 patterns related to electrophilicity.

300 A key advantage of rule-based approaches over more complex methods is that they can
301 be linked with experimental data, literature or expert information that can provide a rationale
302 for predictions. Another decisive factor for their wide application is that experts may derive
303 them even when data are scarce. Therein also lie disadvantages, though, such as the
304 inherently subjective nature of such rule sets⁸³ and the fact that their compilation and
305 maintenance can quickly develop into an expensive and challenging task.

306 Rule sets generally oversimplify chemical and biological properties and cannot account for
307 subtleties in the behaviour and properties of compounds. Consequently, rule-based
308 approaches tend to produce a substantial number of false-positive hits (e.g., compounds
309 matching a PAINS pattern that do not interfere with biological assays). Therefore, the
310 unquestioned use of rule sets entails the risk of rejecting significant numbers of promising,
311 potentially highly innovative compounds^{11,11,44,84–86}. Today, compounds such as acetylsalicylic
312 acid may be excluded from screening decks because of risks associated with chemical
313 reactivity (related to the potential indiscriminate acetylation of many proteins⁸⁷) and selectivity
314 (related to its small size). Cyclosporine, with a molecular weight above 1200 Da, would be lost
315 with any commonly applied molecular weight filter (typically filtering compounds of 600 Da or
316 less). The problem of high false-positive rates is aggravated when rule sets are combined
317 (with the OR logical operator). Only recently have computational approaches become
318 available that enable researchers to analyse and compare sets of SMARTS patterns
319 systematically^{88,89}. On a more technical level, different implementations of rule sets and

320 matching algorithms can yield distinct results. Like for any other model, the applicability
321 domain^{90,91} of individual rule sets (i.e., the property and chemical spaces within which a model
322 produces predictions with defined reliability) must be observed.

323 Similarity-based approaches

324 Similarity-based approaches build on the similar property principle. In the context of assay
325 interference prediction, similarity-based approaches are used primarily to identify potential
326 aggregators⁶⁴: Compounds are flagged as potential aggregators if their molecular structures
327 (typically represented as 2D molecular fingerprints) are similar to those of any known
328 aggregators (similarity typically measured by the Tanimoto coefficient). However, as the
329 number of experimentally confirmed and reported aggregators remains small, the applicability
330 of this guilt-by-association approach remains constrained, mainly because the absence of
331 similarity to any known nuisance compound (aggregator) does not allow any claims on the
332 benign behaviour of a compound.

333 Statistical approaches

334 Statistical approaches leverage historical assay data, typically from large public or
335 corporate bioactivity databases, to describe and predict the frequent hitter behaviour of small
336 organic compounds. This data can be structured as a bioactivity matrix wherein rows and
337 columns represent compounds and assays, respectively, and an entry represents the
338 measured activity of a compound in an assay. Usually, the measured activities (e.g., K_i , K_d ,
339 IC_{50} , EC_{50} , %activity, or %inhibition) are categorised based on a threshold. Of note, such
340 bioactivity matrices are often highly incomplete, as, by far not all compounds are measured in
341 all assays.

342 The most basic approach to defining frequent hitter behaviour rests on bioactivity counts.
343 Bioactivity counts denote the number of assays in which a given compound is reported as
344 active, regardless of the number of assays a compound was tested in and regardless of the
345 relationship between the assays and the target space that they represent^{72,92,93}. Compounds
346 with a bioactivity count above a predefined threshold are deemed to be frequent hitters.
347 Implicitly, this approach assigns an 'inactive' label to all unknown entries in the activity matrix,
348 justified by the general rarity of bioactivity. In consequence, given the nature of bioactivity
349 matrices, such count-based classifications will more likely label older, better-investigated
350 compounds as 'frequent hitters' than modern molecules. Presuming inactivity for unknown
351 matrix entries underestimates a compound's expected number of active entries. This problem

352 can be addressed by using a compound's active-to-tested ratio (ATR) and comparing it to a
353 threshold to identify frequent hitters⁹⁴⁻⁹⁷. Intuitively, this coincides with the assignment of labels
354 to the unknown entries of the bioactivity matrix such that the ratio of active-to-inactive
355 measurements is maintained for each compound.

356 When the assays are independent and identically distributed, the maximum likelihood for a
357 compound's probability of success converges to the ATR as the number of assay
358 measurements increases⁹⁸. If, however, a compound has been tested only in a few assays,
359 the active-to-tested ratio may diverge substantially from the true proportion. Most approaches
360 avoid this scenario by removing compounds that do not exceed a minimum number of assay
361 tests^{94-96,99,100}. This practice, however, leads to the loss of potentially valuable data. Bayesian
362 estimation offers an alternative solution by using a prior ATR to reflect the information that
363 compounds are rarely active in general and have a higher probability of being inactive. The
364 ATR of compounds with limited tests is adjusted towards the prior ATR, while the ATR for
365 those with abundant tests remains largely unaffected. This adjustment is implemented through
366 pseudo counts, where two different constants augment the number of active and inactive
367 measurements for all compounds. This technique was adopted in the Badapple
368 methodology¹⁰¹, although the authors did not precisely follow the underlying theory of the
369 Bayesian estimator in their approach.

370 The approaches for defining frequent hitter behaviour discussed so far are affected by
371 biases of the target space represented in a bioactivity matrix⁷⁰. This problem is commonly
372 addressed by clustering the targets based on protein families⁷⁰ or sequence similarity^{95,96,102}.
373 Another bias in frequent hitter prediction is the unusual hit rates of some assays (e.g.
374 cytochrome P450 assays). For example, when a compound is tested in an assay with an
375 unusually high hit rate, it is likelier to be labelled as a frequent hitter than compounds not tested
376 in that assay. Ghosh et al.⁹⁷ approached this problem by repeatedly shuffling the assay
377 measurements (i.e., the columns of the bioactivity matrix) and recomputing the compounds'
378 ATR values on the rearranged data. The upper confidence interval (95%) of the shuffled ATR
379 values indicates the ATR that can be achieved by chance. A compound is deemed a frequent
380 hitter if the ratio of the observed ATR and the upper confidence interval ratio exceeds a
381 predefined threshold. This technique addresses the problem induced by assays with high hit
382 rates and prevents compounds from being identified as frequent hitters by chance due to
383 limited measured bioactivity values.

384 Instead of estimating the ATR of a compound, the Binomial Survivor Function (BSF)
385 focuses on the average ATR observed on an extensive collection of in-house substances¹⁰³.
386 For a compound, a binomial test is conducted to check whether the observed number of active

387 measurements is unlikely given the fixed ATR and the total number of measurements. David
388 et al.³ have shown empirically that BSF only performs sufficiently well for compounds already
389 tested extensively. In a more recent study, Goodwin et al.¹⁰⁰ showed that the BSF does not
390 adequately represent the PubChem bioactivity matrix regarding rank-order statistics when
391 using a single probability of being active. Furthermore, incorporating different assay hit rates
392 with a Poisson-binomial model improved the results only marginally¹⁰⁰. These findings
393 challenge the approximation that compounds behave like binomial variables with independent
394 and identically distributed assays. Goodwin et al. also emphasise that compound-based
395 models using molecular properties better represent the bioactivity matrix. Based on this
396 insight, machine learning models incorporating compound similarity are the next logical step
397 to enhance frequent hitter detection further.

398 Machine learning approaches

399 Machine learning approaches are unrivalled in identifying and learning subtleties in
400 molecular structures and complex (i.e., non-linear) relationships between molecular features
401 decisive for the behaviour of compounds in biological assays. Today, they represent the main
402 research thrust in computational assay interference prediction.

403 Unlike rule-based approaches, machine learning enables the consideration of the larger
404 molecular context of the substructures defined by rules. In contrast to similarity-based
405 approaches, machine learning goes beyond quantifying global molecular similarity by
406 weighing molecular features.

407 Machine learning approaches are particularly data-hungry. Classical machine learning
408 approaches, such as k-NN, RF and SVM, start to unfold their capabilities when trained on
409 measured data for at least a few hundred compounds (with molecular diversity of the training
410 set being a decisive factor to watch out for). Their full potential generally comes into effect only
411 with large, diverse data sets. The need for large amounts of training data is even more
412 substantial for deep learning approaches, which are often found, with the currently available
413 data sets, not to outperform less complex machine learning methods.

414 Knowledge-sharing approaches, such as transfer learning, multi-task learning and meta-
415 learning, are increasingly employed to mitigate the limitations imposed on machine learning
416 by the chronic shortage of data. These approaches use information from related tasks and
417 data sets to improve the prediction performance¹⁰⁴.

418 Besides data quantity, data quality¹⁰⁵ is of major concern in machine learning. Poor data
419 quality will lead to poor model performance ('garbage in, garbage out'¹⁰⁶). Biases in the data
420 can lead to poor models. They may also lead to the overestimation of model performance (see
421 section 'Data sources for developing models for assay interference prediction' and ref. 66).

422 Machine learning approaches are technically more complex than the other approaches,
423 and the models and predictions are generally more difficult to interpret (although methods for
424 explainable artificial intelligence are maturing and becoming more widely employed¹⁰⁷). The
425 problem of model complexity and interpretability is one reason why machine learning
426 approaches have, in general, a more difficult standing, e.g., in the regulatory context. On the
427 other hand, machine learning models can distil unknown patterns and linear, as well as non-
428 linear structure-property relationships from complex chemical and biological data^{75,108,109}.

429 As for any type of model, users are strongly advised to consider the applicability domain of
430 the machine learning approaches. For example, the generalisation of models for frequent hitter
431 prediction^{95,96} and compound fluorescence prediction⁶⁰ is limited, meaning that predictions for
432 new chemistry may not be reliable. Unfortunately, even today, models published without
433 accompanying applicability domain definitions are still commonplace. Furthermore, many
434 publicly available models do not provide information on the reliability of the individual
435 predictions. For users, this means they may be unable to understand how much (if at all) they
436 can trust in a prediction.

437 Publicly available *in silico* models for assay 438 interference prediction

439 In this section, we discuss publicly available models for assay interference prediction. An
440 overview of all discussed models, including information on how to access these models, is
441 provided in Table 1. Recommendations for the use of *in silico* models are offered in Box 4

442 Rule sets for flagging potential nuisance compounds

443 With approximately 2700 citations of its original publication (all citation statistics referring
444 to CAS SciFinder data), the PAINS rule set² has evolved into one of the most widely employed
445 tools for flagging small molecules that are likely to have an increased risk of causing
446 interference in biological assays. The PAINS rule set has also become a part of the author

447 guidelines of leading journals in small-molecule drug discovery, which is problematic for the
448 reasons mentioned in the Introduction.

449 The PAINS rule set is composed of 480 SMARTS patterns encoding molecular
450 substructures distilled from compound classes for which experiments indicate an increased
451 likelihood of assay interference. The patterns represent a variety of assay interference
452 mechanisms, including covalent modification (e.g. by isothiazolones or ene-rhodanines),
453 redox-cycling (e.g. by catechols and toxoflavin), membrane disruption (e.g. by curcumin), and
454 metal complexation (e.g. by hydroxyphenyl hydrazones)⁸. However, the scope and accuracy
455 of the PAINS concept and rules are limited: The PAINS concept builds primarily on the results
456 and observations from screening a medium-sized molecular library of approximately 93,000
457 compounds on six protein-protein interfaces using a single assay technology, the
458 AlphaScreen. Assay interference observed in the AlphaScreen is often, but not always,
459 indicative of the risk of assay interference in other assay systems¹⁸. Prior to screening, highly
460 reactive compounds were removed from the library. Hence, the PAINS patterns have gaps in
461 the representation of reactive compounds^{2,76}. Screening was generally performed at high
462 concentrations, meaning that the PAINS rules may overemphasise the occurrence of assay
463 interference⁷⁷. Moreover, detergent was added to minimise the aggregation risk, meaning the
464 representation of colloidal aggregation in the PAINS patterns is limited⁷⁷.

465 The PAINS patterns are derived from a synthetic compound library. Hence, application to
466 natural products requires additional considerations²⁶. Moreover, the experimental support of
467 individual PAINS patterns varies greatly. Eighteen of the 480 SMARTS patterns are derived
468 from more than 100 compounds; most patterns are supported by fewer than three
469 compounds^{2,31}. The significance of PAINS pattern matches for individual compounds is often
470 limited, particularly because scaffold decorations can significantly affect the behaviour of small
471 molecules in biological assays, as reported in a systematic study¹¹⁰. Consequently, focusing
472 on a subset of crucial patterns is advisable⁴⁴.

473 Many of the limitations of the PAINS concept are disclosed and discussed in the primary
474 literature^{2,77}. They are also part of an ongoing critical debate^{11,11,19,22,31,85,86,111}. In particular, the
475 relationship between the PAINS and frequent hitter concepts has been the subject of analyses,
476 discussions and some confusion^{14,31,77,97,103,112}. Because the presence of PAINS patterns in
477 individual compounds is merely a risk indicator for assay interference, this means that by far
478 not all compounds matching PAINS patterns indeed cause assay interference or show
479 frequent hitter behaviour. Therefore, it is expected that comparative analyses of historical
480 assay data regarding the frequent-hitter behaviour of compounds that match PAINS patterns

481 versus those that do not find a strong link between the presence of the patterns and frequent-
482 hitter behaviour (see Ref. 77 for an excellent discussion).

483 The PAINS rule set was initially published as Sybyl line notations². The rules were later
484 translated into the more widely used SMARTS language and are accessible via software
485 packages, a KNIME¹¹³ workflow and web services (Table 1). Some groups have published
486 additional rules designed to complement the PAINS rule set^{76,114}. Users should be aware that
487 translating substructural patterns may introduce subtle, technology-related changes, which
488 may cause inconsistent matchings.

489 Besides PAINS, several additional rule sets are relevant to assay interference prediction
490 and detection. In 2005 and 2007, researchers from Abbott Laboratories published a total of
491 175 patterns ('ALARM NMR Rules') encoding substructures that have been linked to causing
492 false-positive readouts due to their reactivity toward thiol groups^{115,116}. During this period, a
493 research team from the Bristol-Myers Squibb (BMS) Pharmaceutical Research Institute
494 published a set of 180 SMARTS patterns encoding functional groups they linked to frequent
495 hitter behaviour⁷². More recently, scientists from GlaxoSmithKline (GSK) R&D
496 Pharmaceuticals published a set of 28 SMARTS patterns encoding substructures linked to
497 frequent hitters present in the GSK compound collection⁷³.

498 Rule sets that cover undesirable moieties beyond those linked to assay interference (i.e.
499 typical screening deck filters) include the Rapid Elimination of Swill (REOS) filters¹¹⁷, a
500 collection of more than 200 patterns typically employed in tandem with physicochemical
501 property criteria, the 'Brenk filters', a collection of more than 100 patterns⁷¹, the 'Lilly rules',
502 which were developed at the Lilly Research Laboratories over almost two decades of
503 research⁷⁰ and have also some of the above-mentioned BMS rules incorporated, and the
504 'NIBR substructure filters', developed at the Novartis Institutes for BioMedical Research
505 (NIBR) for hit finding and triaging⁴⁴.

506 The definitions of all rule sets mentioned herein are publicly available (see Table 1). Scopy,
507 a recently developed Python library, provides easy access to most rule sets¹¹⁸. Several web
508 services are available that allow the filtering of molecular libraries using such rules (see
509 Table 1).

510 Models for frequent hitter prediction

511 The available models for frequent hitter prediction are mostly machine learning models^{3,93–}
512 ^{96,109,119,120}. They are all trained on historical assay data, where, ideally, many structurally

513 diverse compounds are tested against many assays representing a diverse set of
514 biomacromolecules. In reality, the most significant limitation of the existing data sets is the
515 sparsity of the bioactivity matrix. However, the data sets available for modelling frequent hitter
516 behaviour are typically in the range of several hundred thousand compounds screened in
517 hundreds of biological assays and, hence, more extensive than those commonly used for
518 modelling specific types of assay interference.

519 Most models for frequent hitter prediction do not consider or distinguish the mechanisms
520 underlying frequent hitter behaviour or take assay specifics into account. However, some
521 approaches use dedicated models for target-based and cell-based assays⁹⁶. Other
522 approaches aim to distinguish frequent hitters related to assay interference and those related
523 to the genuine modulation of multiple targets¹²¹.

524 Badapple is a statistical model for frequent hitter prediction¹⁰¹. It is derived from a set of
525 nearly 400,000 compounds measured in a total of 822 HTS assays from PubChem. For a
526 compound of interest, Badapple calculates a promiscuity score related to compounds, assays
527 and samples. The score design and a scaffold aggregation strategy aim to increase the
528 method's robustness. During a 5-fold CV, the Pearson correlations obtained for predictions
529 with Badapple and measured data were around 0.90. Several research papers, including the
530 work of Coussens et al.⁹ and De Matos et al.¹²², report using Badapple successfully, usually
531 in combination with other approaches, such as rule sets, to assess the likelihood of compound
532 promiscuity and assay interference.

533 The Bajorath group investigated compound promiscuity, frequent hitter behaviour and the
534 PAINS concept from various angles, considering information on the molecular properties of
535 compounds, their protein interaction partners, and interaction patterns^{123,124}. They published a
536 set of machine learning models (SVM, RF and DNN trained on extended connectivity
537 fingerprints with a width of four bonds -ECFP4- or MACCS structural keys) for discriminating
538 PAINS-matching compounds showing frequent-hitter behaviour from those consistently
539 reported as inactive in biological assays (i.e., compounds consistent with the DCM concept)⁹³.
540 Seventy-four PAINS patterns are represented in both classes of compounds, meaning that
541 the promiscuity behaviour can only be explained and predicted correctly when the structural
542 embedding of the molecular substructures encoded by the PAINS patterns is considered. On
543 a test set generated by random split, the individual models obtained Matthew's correlation
544 coefficients (MCC) of around 0.65 (the MCC is one of the most robust metrics for the
545 performance of binary classifiers. It ranges from -1 to +1, with values above 0.4 generally
546 accepted as an indication of good classification performance).

547 Another set of models coming from the Bajorath group are classifiers discriminating
548 matched molecular pairs (MMPs; these are pairs of molecules that differ only at one position
549 by a single transformation⁴⁸) that represent promiscuity cliffs (i.e. distinct levels of compound
550 promiscuity) from those that do not show such cliffs¹⁰⁹. For model development, a few hundred
551 promiscuity and non-promiscuity cliff MMPs were extracted from PubChem BioAssay and the
552 ChEMBL database and represented by an ECFP4 derivative. On test sets generated by
553 random split, the k-NN, SVM, RF, and DNN models trained on these MMPs consistently
554 outperform models trained on single compounds, with MCC values of up to 0.56 compared to
555 0.42. Again, differences related to the machine learning algorithms employed were minor.
556 Instead, and as expected, model performance strongly depended on the definition of
557 promiscuity cliffs.

558 Hit Dexter⁹⁶, developed by some of us, is a comprehensive web platform for assay
559 interference prediction. The core of this platform is a set of binary classifiers (i.e. multilayer
560 perceptrons) for frequent hitter prediction trained on large subsets of the PubChem BioAssay
561 (molecules represented by Morgan2 fingerprints). Dedicated models for target-based assays
562 and cell-based assays are available. Notably, a protein sequence-based clustering algorithm
563 was employed to merge data obtained for related proteins to reduce the bias in the data (thus
564 avoiding, e.g., kinase inhibitors being marked as frequent hitters simply because they show
565 genuine activity on multiple kinases). When evaluated on holdout data, the most effective
566 models achieved MCC values of up to 0.65, signifying a very strong performance. However,
567 consistent with many machine-learning models derived from molecular fingerprints, the
568 accuracy of predictions was observed to be considerably lower for test compounds structurally
569 dissimilar to those represented in the training data. Therefore, users should always consider
570 the compound-specific reliability indicators provided with predictions. An important finding of
571 this work is that target-based and cell-based assays show distinct frequent hitter behaviour
572 and require dedicated models.

573 We used an earlier version of the Hit Dexter⁹⁵ to profile several compound libraries for the
574 presence of potential frequent hitters. Interestingly, the models classified no more than 2.5%
575 of the Enamine HTS Collection¹²⁵ (a popular commercial screening library) as frequent hitters,
576 suggesting that the compound collection is well curated. In contrast, the models classified up
577 to 14% of known aggregators and a similar percentage of PAINS pattern-matching compounds
578 and natural products as frequent hitters. Interestingly, predictions of the proportion of frequent
579 hitters among approved drugs were in the same range (11% to 13%). Among the natural
580 products, flavonoids (which include quercetin mentioned above) stood out by having up to
581 73% classified as frequent hitters. Overall, these results indicate that the machine learning

582 models can help flag potentially problematic compounds but that a substantial proportion of
583 valuable compounds would be lost if they were trusted blindly.

584 Several research papers report using Hit Dexter to assess the behaviour of compounds of
585 interest in biological assays. However, the existing literature does not allow final conclusions
586 about the tool's value in prospective studies.

587 Recently, Ghosh et al.⁹⁷ released machine learning models specialised in predicting
588 frequent hitters in AlphaScreen assays. The models were trained on approximately 350,000
589 compounds measured during 15 AlphaScreen HTS campaigns (data originating, again, from
590 PubChem BioAssay). Several machine-learning algorithms were explored, including SVM,
591 ASNN, and DNN. The final model, a consensus model composed of three ASNN models and
592 the transformer-CNN model, yielded an averaged balanced accuracy of 85% during 5-fold
593 cross-validation with different data sets.

594 Specialised models

595 Models for colloidal aggregation prediction

596 The development of models for colloidal aggregation prediction is hampered by the lack of
597 available negative data (i.e., confirmed non-aggregators). Researchers have explored
598 different strategies to work with this limitation. For example, Aggregator Advisor⁶⁴ measures
599 the molecular similarity (represented by axonpath fingerprints) to approximately 12,600
600 experimentally confirmed aggregators. Any compound with a Tanimoto coefficient greater
601 than 0.85 (denoting high molecular similarity) or a calculated log P above 3 should undergo
602 experimental aggregation testing. Aggregator Advisor was successfully tested in a prospective
603 study of 40 compounds⁶⁴ and has been widely adopted as a tool to assess the risk of
604 aggregation.

605 It should be noted that the applicability domain of the model's guilt-by-association approach
606 is firmly bound to the chemical space covered by the reference data set of known aggregators.
607 The absence of structural similarity does not indicate the benignity of a compound concerning
608 its behaviour in biological assays.

609 ChemAGG¹²⁶ is a binary classification model (XGBoost classifier trained on ECFP4). It
610 employs the same data set as Aggregator Advisor to represent the positive class (i.e.,
611 aggregators) but utilises, in addition, a set of drugs and drug candidates to represent the
612 negative class (i.e., non-aggregators). Since several drugs and drug candidates are known to

613 be prone to aggregate formation, the modelling setup implies that there may be an increased
614 risk of false-negative predictions, meaning that aggregators may remain undetected (although
615 the authors undertook steps to minimise the number of aggregators present in this data set).

616 Alves et al.⁵⁹ tried to compile cleaner data sets of aggregators and non-aggregators by
617 comparing the behaviour of compounds during HTS with three pairs of assays, each differing
618 primarily by the presence and absence of a detergent. Following this approach, the
619 researchers constructed data sets of approximately 14,000 to 26,000 potential aggregators
620 and roughly up to ten times as many non-aggregators. Notably, the three data sets represent
621 HTS campaigns using distinct assay conditions, which can help investigate the dependency
622 of aggregate formation on assay setups. Following a data balancing procedure, random forest
623 and deep learning models were trained on Morgan fingerprints. On holdout data, the models
624 reached 66% to 77% accuracy. A web service ('SCAM Detective')¹²⁷, offering free access to
625 the random forest models, alerts users about any queries outside a model's applicability
626 domain. Similarity maps visualise which molecule fragments contribute to a compound's
627 classification as aggregator or non-aggregator.

628 Lee et al.¹²⁸ pointed out that the existing models for aggregation prediction neglect a critical
629 factor in aggregation, which concerns the concentrations of the test compounds in the assays.
630 To overcome this limitation, Lee et al. referred to a small data set of less than 1000 compounds
631 measured by DLS consistently at 30 μM concentration. Their prediction tool ('DeepSCAMs')
632 uses a feed-forward neural network architecture with three hidden layers. The model was
633 trained on Morgan fingerprints and 199 physicochemical descriptors. Following promising
634 cross-validation experiments, the authors purchased 65 selected compounds and confirmed
635 the formation of colloidal aggregators for 80% of these compounds in this prospective study.
636 In comparison, fifteen PhD-level medicinal chemists presented with these 65 compounds
637 correctly classified 61% of these compounds, underlining the value of the computational
638 method in decision support.

639 Recently, Molina et al.⁶³ introduced isometric stratified ensembles (ISEs), a widely
640 applicable consensus modelling strategy for improved model performance on large,
641 imbalanced data sets. They employed the new strategy to predict colloidal aggregators at
642 different consensus and applicability domain levels. Depending on the specific test setup and
643 test data set, AUC values of 0.82 for discriminating aggregators and non-aggregators were
644 obtained. The authors evaluated the effectiveness of their approach by comparing it to existing
645 models, albeit not on the identical test set. Consequently, a definitive assessment of the merit
646 of their approach in comparison to existing methods is still pending. Because of the complexity

647 of the ISE approach (using 11 to 17 models constructed on intricate features), the
648 interpretability of the approach is limited.

649 Models for assay interference prediction related to chemical reactivity

650 Assay interference caused by chemically reactive moieties is covered, to some extent, by
651 rule sets and models for frequent hitter prediction (see above). A model specialised in
652 identifying chemically reactive compounds is Xenosite reactivity¹²⁹. This deep convolutional
653 neural network predicts the probability of compounds reacting with nucleophilic trapping
654 agents such as cyanide and GSH, and with biomacromolecules (i.e., proteins and DNA). The
655 model was trained on 2803 nonreactive and reactive compounds. During 10-fold CV, it
656 reached AUC values close to 0.80 in identifying reactive compounds. Xenosite reactivity can
657 also identify sites of reactivity with high accuracy, as demonstrated in several prospective
658 studies^{130–132}. Follow-up work from the developers of Xenosite showed that the model can be
659 of value in particular when used in tandem with the PAINS rule set⁷⁵. Moreover, the model can
660 be combined with other models¹³³ to consider metabolic activation (which may precede
661 chemical reactions).

662 Models for spectroscopic assay interference prediction

663 Several machine-learning approaches for detecting and predicting spectroscopic assay
664 interference have been reported. Publicly available models include InterPred¹³⁴, ChemFLuo⁶⁰,
665 ChemFLuc⁶², and Luciferase Advisor^{61,97}. A recurring theme in the validation studies reported
666 for these tools is the notable sensitivity to assay conditions, such as the particular luciferase
667 enzyme employed, and readout types, including variations in readout wavelengths, on their
668 overall performance.

669 InterPred includes a collection of random forest classifiers for autofluorescence and
670 luciferase inhibition prediction. The models were trained on 8305 compounds (from the
671 Tox21¹³⁵ dataset) measured in counter-screen assays under different assay conditions (i.e.,
672 cell culture conditions, cell types) and assay readout channels (i.e., blue, green and red
673 wavelengths), with molecules represented by 2D molecular and physicochemical descriptors.
674 On holdout data, the models for autofluorescence prediction reached MCC values of 0.44 to
675 0.67 (with lower values obtained for the blue channel). The model for luciferase inhibition
676 prediction reached an MCC of 0.57.

677 ChemFLuo consists of two classifiers for identifying blue and green fluorescent
678 compounds. The technical approach behind ChemFLuo is closely related to ChemAGG.

679 Individual XGBoost models were trained on measured autofluorescence data for
680 approximately 40,000 compounds (blue fluorescence) and approximately 50,000 compounds
681 (green fluorescence), respectively. On external data for blue fluorescence (approximately
682 28,000 compounds), the best model obtained an MCC of 0.34. However, all models showed
683 poor performance on external data for green fluorescence (approximately 323,000
684 compounds), which the authors attribute to issues related to data quality and a limited
685 applicability domain.

686 ChemFLuc is conceptually closely linked to ChemAGG and ChemFLuo. It is an XGBoost
687 classifier trained on ECFP4 representations of a large set of known luciferase inhibitors and
688 noninhibitors (retrieved from PubChem BioAssay). A model generated with this setup obtained
689 an MCC of 0.37 on a test set of 1571 luciferase inhibitors and 56,909 noninhibitors (also
690 retrieved from PubChem BioAssay). The authors merged all available data sets for the final
691 model to use 26,385 luciferase inhibitors and 339,646 noninhibitors for training.

692 Luciferase Advisor is a consensus model comprising four associative neural network
693 models (ASNN). The models were trained on more than 323,000 compounds with measured
694 luciferase inhibition data (retrieved from PubChem BioAssay; inhibitors account for 3.3% of
695 the data set). The molecular structures were represented by large sets of physicochemical
696 descriptors, among which 3D descriptors were important to prediction success. Luciferase
697 Advisor reached a balanced accuracy of 0.90 during five-fold cross-validation.

698 Comprehensive *in silico* platforms

699 Today, comprehensive *in silico* platforms for assay interference prediction are starting to
700 become available. The Hit Dexter platform includes a set of machine learning models for
701 identifying and predicting compounds likely to exhibit frequent hitter behaviour in target-based
702 or cell-based assays (see section 'Models for frequent hitter prediction' for details), two
703 similarity-based approaches for comparing the structures of compounds of interest with those
704 of known aggregators (from Aggregator Advisor) and DCM (from the work of Wassermann et
705 al.¹³⁶), and a pattern matching engine which includes many of the rule sets discussed in the
706 section 'Rule-based approaches'.

707 Recently, Alves et al.¹⁰⁸ reported the development of the LiabilityPredictor platform, which
708 includes the previously developed SCAM Detective models for colloidal aggregation (see
709 section 'Models for colloidal aggregation prediction') plus a new collection of random forest
710 classifiers for predicting assay interference linked to thiol reactivity, redox reactivity, and
711 luciferase (firefly and nano) inhibition. The new models were trained on data sets of

712 approximately 5000 compounds from the NPACT Chemical Library¹³⁷, represented by Morgan
713 fingerprints. In addition to external cross-validation, the models were subjected to prospective
714 validation using sets of 256 compounds per interference mechanism (assay). For the subsets
715 of compounds within the individual models' applicability domains, balanced accuracy was
716 between 58% and 78%.

717 Most recently, ChemAGG, ChemFLuo, and ChemFLuc, all from the same developers, have
718 been integrated into one consistent platform, ChemFH¹³⁸.

719 Computational approaches in practice

720 Today, most rule-based approaches rely on physiochemical properties or SMARTS
721 patterns computed and handled with RDKit, one of the most popular, feature-rich and robust
722 cheminformatics software libraries¹³⁹. RDKit can be accessed from Python and via KNIME, a
723 widely employed data science platform enabling visual (meaning code-free) programming.
724 Most similarity-based approaches also build on these popular components.

725 The more complex tools come with additional code and depend on several software
726 packages, e.g., for machine learning. Although most software packages have permissible
727 licenses and are easy to install, getting the prediction tools to run successfully can involve
728 challenges. Most existing tools result from academic research, meaning their robustness,
729 functionality, platform, and user support may not reach the levels expected from a commercial
730 product. The web services provided for many existing tools mitigate most issues encountered
731 with local installations. However, data security and privacy aspects may be of concern when
732 using web services. Users should consider the recommendations for working with *in silico*
733 models outlined in Box 4.

734 Integrating theoretical and experimental 735 approaches

736 Assay interference poses significant challenges to drug discovery. Because of limitations
737 in prediction accuracy and applicability, *in silico* methods, just like any experimental method,
738 should not be used blindly as a positive or negative compound filter. The most effective
739 strategy to address these challenges is fully integrating the existing theoretical and
740 experimental approaches into the early drug discovery effort. With rule-based approaches,
741 this is already a reality. They are regularly employed in designing screening decks (i.e.,

742 excluding compounds with undesirable molecular moieties or physicochemical properties), in
743 hit finding and hit triage, as exemplified in comprehensive reports and case studies from
744 researchers at NIBR⁴⁴ and the (U.S.) National Institutes of Health⁹. There is a consensus in
745 the scientific community that a high level of caution is required in employing such rule sets.
746 The essence is to keep these rule sets small, simple and interpretable, and to subject them to
747 continuous evaluation and further development.

748 Similarity-based approaches are also popular and regularly employed in drug discovery
749 projects, as Aggregator Advisor exemplifies (more than 300 citations). In contrast, the more
750 complex and recently introduced statistical and machine approaches have only started to
751 receive significant interest from the wider drug discovery community.

752 In addition to their use in screening deck design and hit triage, the *in silico* predictors may
753 also be employed for profiling compound libraries, e.g., to inform the design of screening
754 campaigns or provide compound-specific risk assessments. Furthermore, the use of
755 theoretical approaches for online monitoring of screening processes is highly recommended.
756 The integrated setup enables swift action on potential assay readout anomalies.

757 Conclusions and Outlook

758 A substantial proportion of small organic compounds, including marketed drugs, can trigger
759 false readouts in biochemical or cell-based assays through different interference mechanisms
760 (with aggregation being the most prevalent mechanism). Importantly, assay interference
761 results from the intricate interplay of compound properties and specific assay components.
762 This implies that compounds inducing interference in one assay may exhibit benign behaviour
763 in other assays. While assay interference can impede the directed optimisation of compounds
764 and, hence, pose significant challenges to early drug discovery, it is generally not detrimental
765 to the value of a drug.

766 Experimental approaches and strategies for preventing, detecting and mitigating false
767 assay readouts have come a long way. Today, in addition to these resources, a large number
768 of *in silico* tools for assessing and predicting the compound-specific risk of assay interference
769 are at our disposal. These tools build on straightforward rule-based, similarity-based, and
770 statistical approaches, as well as machine-learning approaches of different levels of
771 complexity.

772 For several reasons, it is difficult to formulate globally valid statements about the
773 performance and applicability of the existing *in silico* tools. Often, the ground truth is unknown.

774 For example, the PAINS patterns match approximately 5% of the approved drugs⁷⁷, and Hit
775 Dexter⁹⁵ flags 11% to 13% of the approved drugs as promiscuous and 5% to 6% as highly
776 promiscuous. Whether these models flag these drugs as potentially problematic for the right
777 or wrong reasons remains to be investigated in most cases. Nevertheless, it is evident that if
778 these models were indiscriminately used as a rigid filter, contrary to their intended purpose,
779 these valuable compounds would have been overlooked and discarded.

780 Most studies evaluating the performance of *in silico* models are of retrospective nature.
781 Moreover, the training and test data are sometimes not disclosed, or the relationship between
782 the training and test data (and hence, the challenges presented by the tests) is not sufficiently
783 understood. Widely accepted benchmark data sets for assay interference predictors are yet
784 to be established. Hence, comparing tools and validation studies is a nontrivial task.

785 Reports of prospective applications of *in silico* approaches are primarily available for the
786 earlier introduced, simpler rule-based and similarity-based approaches. For most machine
787 learning approaches, the number of studies reporting the application of these *in silico* tools
788 does not yet exceed a dozen. Systematic, prospective validation studies, such as those
789 reported for Aggregator Advisor⁶⁴ (compound aggregation prediction), DeepSCAMs¹²⁸
790 (compound aggregator prediction), and LiabilityPredictor¹⁰⁸ (several mechanisms of assay
791 interference) remain rare, likely due to the substantial experimental efforts involved in
792 systematically evaluating *in silico* predictions (a similar situation is observed in the related field
793 of bioactivity prediction¹⁴⁰).

794 Generally speaking, the available computational tools are not yet sufficiently accurate to be
795 used independently for greenlighting or rejecting compounds (exceptions include well-
796 specified, small sets of rules defining undesirable molecular moieties and physicochemical
797 properties), just like it is not advisable to rely on any single bioassay in screening. The rule-
798 based approaches tend to produce false alerts, the similarity-based methods can potentially
799 mislead users to clear compounds just because there is no evidence to suggest that they may
800 be problematic, and the machine learning approaches may be overestimated in their ability to
801 generalise (e.g. due to data biases).

802 That said, many existing *in silico* tools clearly have substantial scientific and practical merit
803 and are recommendable for integration into the early drug discovery infrastructure. In fact, the
804 widespread use of rule-based and similarity-based approaches in screening and screening
805 deck design is already a reality, and the more complex and powerful approaches are now
806 gaining traction quickly. Small-scale research entities, in particular, may benefit strongly from

807 the *in silico* tools as they can emulate, to some extent, domain-specific expertise which may
808 otherwise be out of reach.

809 The significance of the current tools extends beyond what is readily evident in the scientific
810 literature. These models serve as catalysts for respectable efforts by academia and industry
811 to boost these computational approaches as pillars of screening deck design, hit triage, and
812 assay monitoring. Slowing down the adoption and integration of *in silico* tools are usability
813 issues. Also, most models originating from academia are rarely updated ('publish-and-forget').
814 More sustainable maintenance, development and support approaches are required. These
815 could be reached through a coordinated community effort.

816 Stimulated by the increasing accessibility of high-quality, information-rich measured data
817 and new methods, advanced models with superior performance and broader scope will
818 become available in the foreseeable future. These models are expected to utilise metadata to
819 account for the different assay technologies, experimental setups and mechanisms of
820 interference. In this context, large language models (LLMs), such as the one powering
821 ChatGPT, hold great promise, as they enable distilling and interpreting data, e.g. from expert-
822 written assay protocols, and utilising it for predictions. Methods for bias control will be
823 particularly relevant to developing models for frequent hitter prediction as they are commonly
824 trained on large but scarcely populated, highly imbalanced bioactivity matrices.

825 Research into new machine learning algorithms, molecular representations, and
826 explainable artificial intelligence constitute further promising avenues to progress. In
827 particular, deep learning may benefit from federated learning¹⁴¹ and related approaches, which
828 enable collaboration across different research organisations without the need to share private
829 data (see the MELLODDY project as an example¹⁴²). Last but not least, developing and
830 establishing widely accepted, high-quality benchmark data sets enabling thorough,
831 transparent, and reproducible model validation should be recognised as a priority (there is still
832 a long way to go¹⁰⁵).

833 For users of the existing *in silico* tools, the importance of familiarity with the scope and
834 limitations of the individual tools cannot be overstated (Box 4). Users will benefit most from
835 computational tools if they amalgamate, wherever possible, their computational and
836 experimental efforts, e.g., by using *in silico* tools for flagging hits for which the raw assay data
837 should undergo an extra round of vetting or for which further experimental validation in
838 orthogonal assays is in order. Any drug discovery project should involve researchers with
839 expertise in assay technologies and interference. This expertise will also be of great value to

840 interpreting *in silico* predictions, which can be challenging, particularly for machine learning
841 models. If such expertise is unavailable internally, it should be brought in from outside.

842 We hope this Review will enhance awareness of the challenges presented by assay
843 interference in early drug discovery and the current opportunities for addressing these
844 challenges through integrated approaches that combine measurement and computation. We
845 also hope it will encourage many researchers to explore the existing *in silico* tools for assay
846 interference prediction and stimulate their further development and integration into drug
847 discovery pipelines.

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1339 **Competing interests**

1340 C.S. and J.K. are developers of Hit Dexter.

1341 Table 1. In silico models, software, and web services for assay interference
 1342 prediction¹.

Name	Approach	Description	Model training and testing	Year	Refs.	Web services, software
Rule sets for flagging potential nuisance compounds						
PAINS rule set	Rule-based	480 rules encoding scaffolds and substructures linked various mechanisms of assay interference. Not designed to cover aggregators and highly reactive moieties	Trained on an in-house screening library of 93k compounds; evaluated on in-house data	2010	2,77	Orig.: ² Others: ^{82,118,143–148}
Rule set for frequent hitters in AlphaScreen assays	Rule-based	25 SMARTS patterns encoding substructures interfering in AlphaScreen assays with chemistry components or His-tagged proteins. Designed as an extension of the PAINS rule set	Trained and evaluated on in-house and public data sets	2014	76	Orig.: ^{76,80}
Rule set for frequent hitters of GST/GSH interaction	Rule-based	34 SMARTS patterns encoding substructures interfering with GST/GSH interaction (in AlphaScreen assays). Designed as an extension of the PAINS rule set	Trained and evaluated on in-house and public data sets	2016	114	Orig.: ^{80,114}

ALARM NMR Rules	Rule-based	175 SMARTS patterns encoding substructures linked to thiol-reactivity	Trained and evaluated on in-house data	2005	115,116	Orig.: ¹¹⁵ Others: ¹¹⁸
BMS rules	Rule-based	191 SMARTS patterns encoding functional groups linked to frequent hitter behaviour	Trained and evaluated on in-house data	2006	⁷²	Orig.: ⁷² Others: ^{118,148}
GSK rules	Rule-based	28 SMARTS patterns linked to frequent hitter behaviour	Trained and evaluated on in-house data	2018	⁷³	Orig.: ⁷³ Others: ¹⁴⁸
REOS rules	Rule-based	More than 200 SMARTS patterns plus a physicochemical property filter for filtering undesirable compounds	Trained and evaluated on in-house data	1998	¹¹⁷	Orig.: ¹¹⁷ Others: ¹⁴³
Brenk rules	Rule-based	More than 100 SMARTS patterns covering substructures and functional groups undesirable in the drug discovery context. Not focused on assay interference prediction	Trained and evaluated on in-house data	2008	⁷¹	Orig.: ⁷¹ Others: ^{146,148}
Lilly rules	Rule-based	275 SMARTS patterns covering substructures and functional groups undesirable in the drug discovery context. Not focused on assay interference prediction	Trained and evaluated on in-house and external data	2012	⁷⁰	Orig.: ¹⁴⁹ Others: ¹⁴³

NIBR rules	Rule-based	444 SMARTS patterns collected from public and in-house sources for hit identification and triaging	Trained and evaluated on in-house and external data	2020	44	Orig.: ¹⁵⁰ Others: ¹⁵¹
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Models for frequent hitter prediction

Badapple	Statistical	Assigns a promiscuity score based on historical assay data for molecular scaffolds. Considers only molecular scaffolds and not any decorations	Trained on nearly 400k compounds measured in a total of 822 HTS assays; evaluated by cross-validation and additional retrospective analyses	2016	101	Orig.: ¹⁵²
Models classifying PAINS	Machine learning	Set of RF, SVM and DNN models discriminating PAINS pattern-matching compounds behaving as frequent hitters from those acting as DCM. Molecules represented as ECFP4 or MACCS structural keys	Trained on 5223 PAINS pattern-matching frequent hitters and 3059 PAINS pattern-matching, consistently inactive compounds collected from PubChem BioAssay; evaluated on a test set generated by random split	2018	93	Orig.: ¹⁵³
Models predicting promiscuity cliffs	Machine learning	Set of k-NN, SVM, RF and DNN models discriminating MMPs representing promiscuity cliffs from those not representing such cliffs. Molecules represented as ECFP4. Model performance and behaviour are sensitive to the definition of promiscuity cliffs	Trained on a few hundred promiscuity and non-promiscuity cliff MMPs extracted from PubChem BioAssay and ChEMBL; evaluated on a test set generated by random split	2021	109	Orig.: ¹⁵⁴
Hit Dexter	Machine learning	Comprehensive platform including a set of ANNs for discriminating non-promiscuous, promiscuous and highly promiscuous compounds. Dedicated models for target-based and cell-based assays. Molecules	Trained on more than 250k compounds measured in at least 100 assays for distinct proteins; evaluated on holdout data consisting of approximately 25k compounds, plus a DCM data set (approx. 20k to 40k	2021	96	Orig.: ¹⁴⁸

represented as Morgan fingerprints. Characteristic of fingerprint-derived models, the extrapolation capability of these models is constrained (compounds) and a set of approx. 1000 known bad actors

OCHEM model for frequent hitter prediction in AlphaScreen assays	Machine learning	Consensus model of ANNs for predicting frequent hitters in AlphaScreen assays. Models use a variety of 2D and 3D descriptors	Trained on approx. 350k compounds measured during 15 AlphaScreen HTS campaigns; evaluated by cross-validation plus on external test sets	2022	97	Orig.: ¹⁵⁵
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In silico models for colloidal aggregation prediction

Aggregator Advisor	Similarity-based	Flags compounds structurally related to known aggregators or with log <i>P</i> values above 3 for experimental evaluation of their aggregation behaviour. The absence of an alert is not an indicator of benign compound behavior in biological assays	Trained on a public data set of approx. 12k known aggregators. Tested in a prospective study of 40 compounds	2015	64	Orig.: ¹⁵⁶ Others: 144
ChemAGG	Machine learning	XGBoost classifier trained on ECFP4. Because drugs and drug-like compounds are used to present non-aggregators, there may be an increased risk of missed aggregators.	Trained on approx. 12k aggregators represented by the Aggregator Advisor data set (see above) plus approx. 24k non-aggregators represented by a subset of drugs and drug candidates; evaluated by cross-validation and on holdout data	2019	126	Orig.: ¹³⁸
SCAM Detective	Machine learning	RF classifier trained on Morgan fingerprints. Warns users about predictions outside the applicability domain.	Trained on approx. 60k non-aggregators and putative aggregators from an AmpC β -lactamase quantitative	2020	59	Orig.: ¹²⁷

Visualisation of the molecular fragments contributing to the classification of a compound as (non-) aggregator

HTS screen and approx. 50k compounds measured in a cruzain quantitative HTS, extracted from PubChem BioAssay; evaluated on large sets of holdout data

DeepSCAMs	Machine learning	Feed-forward neural network trained on Morgan fingerprints and physicochemical properties	Trained on DLS data for 916 compounds measured at consistently at 30 μ M concentration; prospective validation based on 65 compounds, in competition with a panel of medicinal chemists	2021	¹²⁸	Orig.: ¹⁵⁷
Isometric Stratified Ensembles (ISEs)	Machine learning	Consensus modelling strategy predicting (non-) aggregators at different consensus and applicability domain levels	Trained on three sets of up to 190k compounds measured in HTS, extracted from PubChem BioAssay. Tested on large internal and external test sets	2022	⁶³	¹⁵⁸

Models for assay interference prediction related to chemical reactivity

XenoSite reactivity	Machine learning	DNN model predicting assay interference caused by chemically reactive compounds. Can be combined with other models ¹³³ to consider metabolic activation	Trained on 2803 reactive and nonreactive compounds. Tested by cross-validation and with an external test set of 14 compounds	2016	¹²⁹	Orig.: ¹²⁹
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Models for spectroscopic assay interference prediction

InterPred	Machine learning	Set of random forest classifiers for predicting assay interference caused by autofluorescence or luciferase	Trained on 8305 compounds included in the Tox21 data set and measured in counter-screen assays	2020	⁴⁷	Orig.: ^{134,159}
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inhibition. Trained on 2D molecular and physicochemical descriptors. Individual models for representing different assay conditions

under different conditions; evaluated on external sets of 22 to 258 compounds

ChemFLuo	Machine learning	Two XGBoost models for predicting blue and green autofluorescence. Trained on ECFP4. Known to have limited extrapolation capability. Model performance may also be impacted by the limited quality of the training data	Trained on approx. 40k and 50k compounds from PubChem BioAssay, measured in blue and green autofluorescence counter-screens, respectively; evaluated on approx. 28k and 323k compounds from PubChem BioAssay, respectively (from distinct assays)	2021	60	Orig.: ¹³⁸
Luciferase Advisor	Machine learning	Consensus model of four associative neural network models. Trained on a large set of physicochemical descriptors	Trained on approx. 323k compounds measured in different luciferase inhibition assays (from PubChem BioAssay); evaluated primarily by cross-validation	2018	61	Orig.: ¹⁶⁰
ChemFLuc	Machine learning	XGBoost model for predicting luciferase inhibition. Trained on ECFP4	Trained on approx. 366k compounds measured in different luciferase inhibition assays (from PubChem BioAssay); evaluated on data set from PubChem BioAssay (from distinct assays)	2020	62	Orig.: ¹³⁸

Comprehensive in silico platforms for assay interference prediction

Hit Dexter	Various	Features machine-learning models for frequent hitter prediction, similarity-based approaches for aggregator and DCM identification, and rule sets for flagging	Trained and evaluated primarily on data from PubChem BioAssay	2021	96	Orig.: ¹⁴⁸
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nuisance compounds

LiabilityPredictor	Machine learning	Featuring machine learning models for assay interference prediction related to thiol reactivity, redox reactivity, luciferase inhibition and aggregation (from SCAM Detective)	Trained on multiple data sets, most of which consist of approx. 5k compounds from NPACT ¹⁶¹ ; evaluated by external cross-validation plus prospective experimental validation with 256 compounds per assay	2023	108	Orig.: ¹⁶²
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1343 ¹ Abbreviations: ANN, artificial neural network; DCM, dark chemical matter; DLS, dynamic light scattering; DNN, deep neural network; ECFP4,
1344 Extended Connectivity Fingerprints with a width of four bonds; GSH, glutathione; GST, glutathione S-transferase-glutathione; HTS, high-
1345 throughput screening; ISE, isometric stratified ensemble; k-NN, k-nearest neighbour; MACCS, Molecular ACCess System; MMP, matched
1346 molecular pair; RF, random forest; SVM, support vector machine.

1347 Box 1. Terminology

1348 Hits

1349 Compounds that trigger a signal, typically indicative of biological activity, in biochemical or
1350 cell-based assays or in silico testing systems. 'Hit' does not imply the existence of conclusive
1351 evidence of genuine bioactivity. True hits exhibit genuine bioactivity on the target
1352 biomacromolecule; false hits trigger assay signals via different interference mechanisms.

1353 Bad actors or nuisance compounds or Compounds Interfering with an Assay 1354 Technology (CIATs)³

1355 Chemically heterogeneous group of compounds interfering with certain assay technologies,
1356 irrespective of the underlying mechanism and frequency of occurrence of the assay
1357 interference phenomena. In the context of natural products research, they are also called
1358 Invalid Metabolic Panaceas (IMPs)⁴.

1359 Assay interference does not exclude true bioactivity; it just makes bioactivity more
1360 challenging to detect and optimise.

1361 Pan-assay interference compounds (PAINS)²

1362 Molecules built on scaffolds that have been linked to pan-assay interference. The 480
1363 patterns describing these substructures are derived from a proprietary compound library,
1364 screened at high concentrations with six AlphaScreen assays. The screening deck does not
1365 include highly reactive compounds, and aggregation was suppressed by adding a detergent.

1366 'PAINS' is often used as a synonym for bad actors, nuisance compounds, or frequent
1367 hitters, although the PAINS concept covers only a subset of these challenging compounds.

1368 Aggregators³⁰ or Small, Colloidally Aggregating Molecules (SCAMs)⁵⁹

1369 Molecules forming colloidal aggregates when the compound's critical aggregation
1370 concentration (CAC) is exceeded. They are typically characterised by poor water solubility
1371 related to large, hydrophobic (and aromatic) surface areas^{63,64,163,164}.

1372 Chemically reactive compounds

1373 Molecules carrying chemically reactive moieties that can form covalent bonds with
1374 biomacromolecules and other assay components. They include desired, specific covalent
1375 modulators of target biomacromolecules but also chemical breakdown products and

1376 impurities. Chemically reactive moieties alter assay readouts even when present only in
1377 traces. They are challenging to detect with analytical methods.

1378 **Frequent hitters**⁵

1379 Substances showing higher-than-expected hit rates in distinct biological assays. Most
1380 cases of frequent hitter behaviour are caused by bad actors, reactive chemical breakdown
1381 products and impurities, particularly when observed across technologically distinct assays.
1382 Fewer cases are the result of (true) promiscuous binding. Molecular properties such as
1383 lipophilicity, molecular weight, and charged groups can affect compound promiscuity^{44,163,165–}
1384 ¹⁷⁰.

1385 **(Truly) promiscuous compounds or promiscuous binders**

1386 Subset of frequent hitters which interact specifically, reversibly with multiple, distinct
1387 biomacromolecules¹⁷¹. They should not be equated to nuisance compounds as they may be
1388 valuable starting points for developing innovative therapeutics, especially in the context of
1389 polypharmacology^{11,86,121,124,172–175}. A major challenge in working with such compounds will be
1390 the optimisation of their selectivity and safety profiles^{11,44,168,174}.

1391 **Privileged scaffolds**

1392 Molecular scaffolds enabling compounds to interact with various biomacromolecules by
1393 matching the pharmacophoric and steric requirements of multiple ligand binding sites¹⁷⁶.

1394 **Dark chemical matter**¹³⁶

1395 Compounds confirmed as inactive across a wide range of assays and targets. They can be
1396 particularly interesting to medicinal chemists because these compounds may have a
1397 favourable selectivity and, hence, safety profile¹³⁶.

1398 **Box 2. Types and sources of assay interference**

1399 **Generalised assay interference**

1400 **Colloidal aggregation**

1401 Most common type of assay interference, although strongly dependent on assay conditions
1402 (e.g., compound concentrations and presence or absence of detergent)^{23,30,37,177–179}. Colloidal
1403 aggregation involves the formation of large particles that bind thousands of protein molecules,

1404 causing protein sequestration and partial or local denaturation^{180,181}. Smaller particles
1405 mimicking a protein binding partner have also been described¹⁸².

1406 **Chemical reactivity**

1407 Assay interference linked to non-specific modification of biomacromolecules (or other
1408 assay components) by chemically reactive compounds. Common reactions include redox
1409 reactions, the formation of disulfide bonds, and reactions of nucleophilic protein components
1410 with electrophilic moieties of compounds (particularly Michael addition reactions and
1411 nucleophilic aromatic substitutions)^{7,38}.

1412 **Metal chelation**

1413 Formation of stable complexes with metal ions. For some drugs, chelate formation is
1414 essential to efficacy^{183,184}. The interference is caused by the depletion of metal ions essential
1415 to the assay, inhibition of metalloenzymes, formation of coloured or fluorescent chelates, and
1416 other effects^{8,38}.

1417 **Membrane disruption**

1418 Assay interference caused by the loss of membrane-bound proteins, formation of
1419 precipitates, or changes to assay conditions⁸.

1420 **Technology-related assay interference**

1421 **Light-based interferences**

1422 Because of the popularity of spectroscopic assays, these are among the most relevant
1423 types of technology-related assay interference. Assay interference caused by light signal
1424 attenuation includes fluorescence quenching (energy of a fluorophore, such as in fluorescein
1425 or rhodamines, in an excited state, is transferred to an interference compound), absorbance
1426 (light at wavelengths relevant to the detection system of the assay is absorbed by the
1427 interference compound), interference with reporter enzymes (can involve the direct inhibition
1428 of reporter enzymes such as luciferase by the interference compound or the attenuation of
1429 light signals emitted as a result of the activity of reporter enzymes), and light scattering
1430 (insoluble materials such as colloidal aggregates cause the diffraction of light).

1431 Assay interference caused by light signal emission includes the autofluorescence of a
1432 compound (which can cause, e.g., false-positive signals and the deterioration of the signal-to-

1433 noise ratio) and chemiluminescence (where a chemical reaction results in the emission of a
1434 light signal).

1435 **Interferences in homogeneous proximity assays**

1436 Homogenous proximity assays include, e.g., the AlphaScreen (amplified luminescent
1437 proximity homogeneous assay), FRET (fluorescence resonance energy transfer), TR (time-
1438 resolved) FRET, and BRET (bioluminescence resonance energy transfer) assays.
1439 Interferences associated with proximity assays are primarily caused by signal
1440 attenuation/emission or disruption in the capture systems⁷.

1441 **Assay interference caused by compound breakdown products** 1442 **and impurities**

1443 Chemical breakdown products can be formed over time or, e.g., in the presence of assay
1444 reagents. Impurities commonly originate from synthesis or are introduced through
1445 contamination.

1446 Major publishers of scientific literature and funding bodies require compounds to be at least
1447 95% pure, typically confirmed by high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
1448 (HPLC–MS). However, some breakdown products and impurities may falsify assay readouts
1449 even when present only in traces. Even the most advanced compound management and
1450 analytical chemistry approaches may fail to identify some problematic impurifications.
1451 Therefore, re-synthesis and purification of the most interesting compounds may prove
1452 indispensable.

1453 **Box 3. Experimental approaches for tackling assay** 1454 **interference**

1455 **Colloidal aggregation**

1456 Colloidal aggregation is often (but not always) linked with steep hill slopes^{14,23,185,186} (see
1457 Figure 2) that can be detected by dose-response curve analysis. However, steep hill slopes
1458 may also arise, e.g., from covalent binding.

1459 Detergents are used to disrupt colloidal structures, reduce aggregation formation, and
1460 prevent nonspecific protein adsorption. Bioactivity lost under detergent-containing conditions
1461 is a strong indicator of interference by colloidal aggregation^{177,187}. Detergent conditions are
1462 also part of counter-screen setups using aggregator-sensitive enzymes such as AmpC β -
1463 lactamase^{23,177,185}.

1464 Screening at lower concentrations (i.e. below the CAC) circumvents aggregation (but may
1465 lead to the loss of weak binders³⁷). Increasing enzyme concentration leads, for low K_d values
1466 (as is the case for aggregators), to a linear increase of IC_{50} values^{37,186}, while the IC_{50} values
1467 of non-aggregators remain largely unaffected.

1468 Further methods to detect and tackle assay interference include dynamic light scattering
1469 (DLS; determines the size distribution of particles in the sample^{23,9,187,188}), centrifugation
1470 (causing aggregates to precipitate¹⁸⁷; hence, bioactivity lost by centrifugation is likely linked to
1471 colloidal aggregates), NMR (detecting aggregators by changes in NMR spectral attributes¹⁸⁹),
1472 microscopic methods (detecting aggregators, e.g., through their non-specific (fluorescence)
1473 protein binding behaviour¹⁸⁷ or direct visualisation of aggregators in transmission electron
1474 microscopy - TEM^{187,190}), and surface plasmon resonance (SPR; detecting the binding of
1475 aggregators to protein, provided that the protein target can be immobilised¹⁹¹). For a
1476 comprehensive discussion, see Ref.³⁷

1477 Chemical reactivity

1478 Assay interference linked to chemical reactivity can be addressed with time-resolved
1479 measurements (covalent binders commonly show an increasing inhibitory effect over time<sup>192-
1480 195</sup>), 'jump-dilution experiments' (involving the drastic dilution of the test compound with the
1481 target into a substrate-rich environment, by which reversible binders show a significant
1482 reduction of target inhibition while the activity of irreversible binders remains largely stable<sup>196-
1483 198</sup>), dialysis³⁸ (during which reversible binders are effectively removed from the protein target
1484 whereas irreversible binders stay bound to the target), use of scavenging agents such as
1485 dithiothreitol (which can bind thiol-reactive compounds that otherwise may bind to the thiol
1486 groups of cysteine residues^{38,41}), ALARM NMR (an NMR-based method detecting the binding
1487 of thiol-reactive compounds^{115,9,41}), and the horseradish peroxidase-phenol red (HRP-PR)
1488 assay (detecting redox-cycling compounds by changes in the absorbance spectrum of phenol
1489 red^{38,199}). For a comprehensive discussion, see Ref.³⁸.

1490 Technology-related assay interference

1491 **Fluorescence-based assays**

1492 Fluorescence interference can be addressed by pre-reading fluorescence signals (after
1493 incubation of a compound and before the addition of substrate³³), fluorescence spectroscopic
1494 profiling (providing a comprehensive assessment of the fluorescence spectra of test
1495 compounds to inform on possible interference²⁰⁰), using red-shifted fluorophores (tackling
1496 assay interference linked to autofluorescence observed in the blue and green regions of the
1497 spectrum²⁰⁰), and using fluorophores with long half-lives (enabling measurements after the
1498 decay of auto-fluorescence^{33,201}). Better signal-to-background ratios can be obtained with
1499 kinetic approaches, where the assay readouts are registered over time²⁰². For a
1500 comprehensive discussion, see Ref. ³³.

1501 **Bioluminescence-based assays**

1502 Bioluminescence-based assays typically include a luciferase component²⁰³. Compounds
1503 interfering with luciferase are typically detected with luciferase inhibition assays²⁰⁴. Orthogonal
1504 assays using structurally distinct luciferases (with a limited inhibitor overlap) can help validate
1505 compound activity²⁰⁵. Coincidence reporter systems in cell-based assays^{206–208} can test and
1506 validate compound activity by co-expressing (in cells) a pair of luciferases with limited inhibitor
1507 overlap. Compounds triggering signals from both reporter enzymes are more likely to exhibit
1508 genuine bioactivity. For a comprehensive discussion, see Ref. ³⁴.

1509 **Homogeneous proximity assays**

1510 Homogeneous proximity assays primarily utilise light-based detection technologies. Hence,
1511 methods tackling interference in these assays share commonalities with those outlined above.
1512 Changing the capture component may also help tackle assay interference while not affecting
1513 true hits. For a comprehensive discussion, see Ref. ⁷.

1514 **Box 4: Recommendations for working in silico** 1515 **models for assay interference prediction**

1516 To make the best use of the existing *in silico* models for assay interference prediction,
1517 researchers should familiarise themselves with the models by carefully reading the relevant
1518 scientific publications and documentation. Validation studies, even those published in peer-

1519 reviewed journals, should always be critically scrutinised (see Ref. ²⁰⁹ for a contemporary
1520 discussion of how, in particular, machine-learning models should be evaluated).

1521 Users should ensure that the input for predictions (usually molecular structures) is prepared
1522 according to the models' requirements (e.g., consideration of protonation states).

1523 Rather than relying on a single model, users should carefully select a set of models to
1524 combine. In particular, the combination of models trained on distinct data sets and types of
1525 data and models utilising orthogonal representations (of molecular and biological properties)
1526 and modelling algorithms will likely deliver a more accurate and comprehensive picture of the
1527 assay interference risk for a compound, based on which better-informed decisions can be
1528 made.

1529 Users should observe the scope and applicability domains of the individual models
1530 concerning the coverage of chemical space and types of assay interference. Associated with
1531 that, they should consider the estimated reliability of the predictions for individual compounds.
1532 Extra caution should be exercised when using models that do not provide information on their
1533 applicability domain, the reliability of individual predictions, or detailed information on the data
1534 sets on which they were trained and validated.

1535 Users should consider predictions as risk indicators rather than evidence for a compound's
1536 bad or benign behaviour in biological assays. Accordingly, predictions should generally be
1537 used for flagging compounds but not rejecting them.

1538 The software license terms require consideration, as well as data security and privacy
1539 aspects, particularly when using web services.

1540 Short summary

1541 Biological assays are essential to pharmaceutical, agrochemical and cosmetics research.
1542 However, false readouts pose significant challenges in screening small molecules. This
1543 publication reviews methods and strategies for tackling assay interference, focusing on
1544 computational approaches and their integration with experimental methods.